

TEACHING CHILDREN WITH MOWING SKILLS TO SPEAK

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Abstract. *Teaching visually impaired children to speak a foreign language creates certain difficulties due to a number of features in child pathology. First, speech disorders occur when many visually impaired children speak their native languages, which affect foreign language acquisition. Secondly, the impoverishment of emotional experience and a decrease in cognitive activity affect the volume of the child's vocabulary. Thirdly, slow perception causes many repetitions and an increase in interruptions.*

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Teaching visually impaired children to speak a foreign language creates certain difficulties due to a number of features in child pathology. First, speech disorders occur when many visually impaired children speak their native languages, which affect foreign language acquisition. Secondly, the impoverishment of emotional experience and a decrease in cognitive activity affect the volume of the child's vocabulary. Thirdly, slow perception causes many repetitions and an increase in interruptions. Nevertheless, on the basis of the formation of communicative competence, which is the final result of mastering the science of "foreign language", lies eloquence. For this reason, teaching visually impaired children to speak a foreign language is one of the main tasks of the teacher.

Motive is the basis for the creation of any action, including speech. In order for the student to develop a passion for participation in communication, the task of the teacher is to create a speech situation in the classroom, when we consider teaching oral communication in two different forms, such as monological and dialogical:

A monologue is "an individual's appeal to most listeners" [6.]. Aspects such as pursuit of purpose, perfection of meaning, logic, continuous character, independence are aspects specific to the monologue. In the methodology of our country of teaching foreign languages, there are two different ways of teaching a monologue: "top-down" and "bottom-up". The first method provides for the formation of monological skills based on the text read using supports. In the second case, monological skills are formed without supports to the text. We believe that the "top-down" method is more suitable for teaching speech with visually impaired children, since such children are recommended to be taught using various supports, including textual ones.

In our view, "the ESA" educational model such as Engage, Study, Activate – attract, reap, apply is an effective way to form monological skills in visually impaired children. This method is used by the English stylist D. Designed and presented by Harmer. The essence of "the ESA" is that there are three stages of learning in the lesson: attraction, learning and application.

The teacher applies organizational and methodological skills at the stage of involvement. It organizes the learning process so that students can actively work. To attract the attention of students, they can show illustrations or speeches on the topic of the lesson, videos, small stage appearances, parses from films or cartoons, tell anecdotes, read fairy tales and articles. Visual material is necessary to be built on the basis of the lexicon that students use in the lesson.

Students read text at the learning stage, perform exercises, familiarize themselves with the new lexicon, learn grammatical constructions. The purpose of this stage is to show how to apply the lesson material in practice.

Students go out to communicate in a different language during the application phase. They can discuss a specific topic, debate, play role-playing games, perform excerpts from a small scene, and exhibit their monologues. At this stage, the teacher sees to what extent the children have mastered the material of the lesson.

A clear example is the use of the ESA in the education of visually impaired children. Yu.A. Komarova, I.V. Larionova and J. The Perrettes ' "English. Brilliant's textbook "for Grades 4" after studying the "Food" section, the teacher conducts a reinforcement-lesson based on the material mentioned. At the stage of attraction at the beginning of the lesson, the teacher shows the Class A video about the dish, in which pictures with the name of the dish in the image are shown. It would be nice to find a video in which words are spoken by the announcer so that the children can repeat after him. there are a lot of similar videos on the Internet. Students memorize the lexical item "Food" after watching the video during the learning phase. The teacher draws a cluster on the board for exhibitionism according to figure 3.2.1.

- Cluster to " Food " theme

Students also repeat grammatical constructions I have/haven't got some/any I There is/isn't some/any, There are/aren't some/any after repeating the lexicon as well as interrogative and exclamation forms of the constructions in question. Children compose a monologue using these constructions. Students read text about food from a textbook, repeating lexical and grammatical materials.

Students perform the following exercises during the application phase:

8) Draw a trolley with your favourite food. Say what you have got in your trolley [65, P. 49]. The teacher prepares a basket or box in which a picture of the dish is described in advance, signed leaflets with the appropriate word, and students board leaflets. Children take turns going to the board, putting flyers with their favorite food in the basket and telling the class what is in the basket. It is a small monologue in the form of a play that tells the story of his preferred food.

9) dialogue is an exchange of ideas between two individuals or a conversation between two individuals. The dialogue is characterized by reactivity, situational relevance and randomness. Like monological discourse, dialogue is taught through the "top-down" and "bottom-up" method.

In our eyes, it is preferable to use the “top-down” method at the initial stage of teaching dialogical skills to visually impaired schoolchildren.

For visually impaired children, dialogical speech can cause more difficulties than monological one. Much in communication will depend on the attitude of the interlocutor, his response. Dialogical communication in their native language is difficult for visually impaired children, which affects their foreign language speaking.

When teaching in a foreign language, the teacher should first start the lesson by asking questions to the class. Traditionally, the lesson begins with questions about health, weather and non-arrivals.

We believe that the teacher at the beginning of the lesson should develop small dialogues for him if there is a visually impaired child in the classroom. Including How are you? asking the question " Oh, What a pity! Why aren't you fine? or what happened? to get a negative response from the child and, at the end, to be encouraged by the words don't worry, Everything will be OK, etc.k.

In such a way, it is possible to develop dialogue on any topic. It is necessary to ask what the child ate for breakfast and see if he liked it, what he liked to eat for breakfast, lunch and dinner. Thus, the teacher organizes the intense activity of students at the beginning of the lesson and develops the skills of conducting dialogue. It is permissible not to forget that there are also non-communicative tools.

The use of gestures, facial expressions, pantomimics, movements of the head, hands, body helps to predict the mood of the interlocutor and form a pre-response to the note. In addition to visually impaired students, it is necessary to encourage normatively developing students to express emotions using non-verbal means.

Yu.A.Komarova, I.V.Larionova and J.The perrettes ' “English. Consider the formation of dialogical skills on the example of the textbook exercises” Brilliant” for Grades 4”. Students are given new words meaning different school subjects. The teacher displays pictures on an interactive whiteboard, reads words, and students repeat after it. After learning the lexicon, the teacher takes a board with what's your favourite lesson? write, and with the readers, Jor repeats the question in the voice. They then do (9) Talk to your friend about your favourite lessons [7]. students independently perform mini-dialogues on a textbook sample, asking each other about their favorite subjects. Teacher Wow! Oh really? That's good! Etc.k. using phrases, it asks readers to answer the question. The result is a smaller dialogue, including:: what's your favourite lesson? - Geography- Oh, really? My favourite lesson is Geography too!

Analyzing the features of working with visually impaired children, we have developed the following methodological recommendations for teaching such children in elementary schools:

1) in order for passion to appear in students, it is necessary to interest them. To do this, the teacher applies visual aids, creates problem situations, performs mini-dialogues, etc.k.

2) The Teacher is required to create an atmosphere of communication in each lesson. This means that the teacher and the student will be speech partners, and it is necessary that there is a continuous interaction between them.

3) when teaching visually impaired children to monological and dialogical speech, it would be advisable to use the “top-down” method, which provides for teaching text-based oral speech.

4) various methods are recommended for learning to speak

5) including the ESA: Engage, Study, Activate. This method consists of three stages. The teacher first engages the students in the learning process, then explains the material to them, and finally, the students go out to communicate in a different language.

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